

Mayasaṃgraha and *Bhāvacūḍāmaṇi* introduction

Mayasaṃgraha manuscript A:

NAK 1.1537, NGMPP reel number A31/18. Palm leaf, 28x4.5cm. 25 folios. 6 lines to a side. Incomplete. Newari script.

This, the only available manuscript of the *Mayasaṃgraha*, is incomplete. While much is missing, what is there is clear and carries few difficulties. I here present the portions of chapter 4 that are available. At f18r, chapter 4 is already underway and we cannot know how many verses of it are missing. I will label the missing verses x. The first verse at f18r will thus be called x+1. Further on in the chapter, we lack another set of verses. This lacuna I will denote as y. I then call the first verse after the gap y+1.

In the apparatus I will label the manuscript A.

Bhāvacūḍāmaṇi manuscript C:

A copy of a commentary to the *Mayasaṃgraha*: the *Bhāvacūḍāmaṇi* of Bhaṭṭa Vidyākāṇṭha. Jammu, Shri Raghunath Temple MSS Library, 5291, now in the collection of the Ranbir Research Institute, Jammu; paper; Kashmirian Devanāgarī. 16 lines to a side.

In notes I will refer to the commentary as MYcomm. In the apparatus to the commentary I will label it C.

Contents of chapter 4:

x+1-x+6	location of śalyas according to horoscope
x+7-x+12	location of śalyas according to āya
x+13ab	location of śalyas according to sighting of a dog or jackal
x+13cd-21ab	location of śalyas according to itches
y+1cd	the 8x8 kṣetra for a temple
y+2-5b	the 33x33 kṣetra for a deśa
y+5c-811b	the 5x5 kṣetra for a funeral ground
y+11c-13	abhyarcana and homa
y+14-35	bali offerings to the deities of the vāstu body
y+36	homa
y+37-39	japa